

ACOUSTIC RETROREFLECTORS FOR MUSIC PERFORMANCE MONITORING

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ABSTRACT

This paper is concerned with acoustic retroreflectors, which reflect sound back towards any sound source. They are constructed here of two reflecting panels connected with hinges and placed on a hard reflecting floor. Acoustic retroreflectors can replace electroacoustic monitoring in music performance when sufficiently large panels are placed at an appropriate distance from performers. A good distance is between about 3 and 8 m from a player, corresponding to propagation delays of between approximately 20 ms and 50 ms from a player to the retroreflector and back. We have conducted acoustic measurements in an anechoic chamber using various retroreflector structures, including symmetric V-shaped and asymmetric L-shaped reflectors of two different heights with various opening angles and incident angles. Our data show that the 90° opening angle produces the strongest reflection. Surprisingly, increasing the opening angle to 100° or more decreases the magnitude of reflection by more than 10 dB, while a smaller angle, such as 80°, mainly weakens the reflection at high frequencies. User tests with musicians indicate that acoustic retroreflectors can provide the desired feedback in performance spaces in which natural reflections to the stage are missing, such as in large halls far away from the walls or outdoors.

1. INTRODUCTION

For a performer, some places are easy to play in while others are difficult. This ease or difficulty is related to the reflections of the performance space sending the player's own sound back to her or his ears [1]. Without such auditory feedback provided by the walls or other reflective structures, the performer does not hear her or his playing well, which feels uncomfortable. This influences especially amateurs. Professionals notice this as well, but they are more competent to make adjustments. Through experience they look for a better position to stand or sit and their muscle memory helps them to maintain good ergonomics even when the space does not support the sounds they are making. Reflections that are too early or too late do not help (see Fig. 1).

This paper considers a light-weight acoustic arrangement corresponding to 'stage monitor speakers' used in amplified music performances. The function of monitoring is

for players to hear their own performance and also a mix of other performers. How much monitoring feedback is needed, and how can this be implemented acoustically without building heavy structures on the stage? Can a portable set of good reflectors be made which can be carried by performers themselves to schools, museums, outdoor places, and other environments not allowing a loudspeaker-based monitoring system?

Figure 1. Rough division of usefulness of retroreflections in music and speech performances.

This paper suggests acoustic retroreflectors, which are constructed of three orthogonal acoustically reflective boards: two boards connected together at a right angle placed on a hard floor, which acts as the third board. Such a retroreflector echoes sound back towards a sound source placed at any angle in its vicinity [1, 2]. The best location for a retroreflector is inevitably in front of the performers, i.e., between the players and the audience. This implies that the construction must not be visually intrusive. The main emphasis in this work is to find low, ramp-like constructions, that can be hidden among chairs and music stands. Furthermore, knowing how far on the side of an ensemble a retroreflector can be installed while still working efficiently, is of interest. This is, in practice, connected to finding out how wide a horizontal range of angles can be covered with one retroreflector, i.e., how large a group of performers can benefit from each reflector. This paper does not consider what the audience hears, although good stage acoustics may greatly improve a music performance.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows. Sections 2 and 3 discuss the basics of reinforcing sound reflections and acoustic reflectors. Section 4 explains our arrange-

ments for measuring the performance of acoustic retroreflectors. Section 5 analyzes the results of the acoustic measurements, section 6 presents user experiments conducted with performers, and section 7 concludes the paper.

2. REFLECTIONS ARE IMPORTANT

General room acoustics theory has shown that the listener's impression of a room, its envelopment by music and other similar features is formed by sound information (preferably lateral) that arrives 30 to 100 ms after the direct sound [1, 3, 4]. This has been corroborated in many ways through studies of audience experience.

Some literature on stage acoustics exists [4] but noticeably less. Even less can be found about music making in smaller ensembles and in non-concert-hall environments.

If the first reflected sound reaches the performer only after 50ms (corresponding to a distance of 8.5 m), the risk that the performer perceives an audible echo is greatly increased, making singing, playing and even talking very difficult. This phenomenon is not uncommon in long festivity halls of the 19th and 20th centuries. To free performers of this bad situation, it often suffices to add an extra reflection in the range 30–40 ms. Additional delayed sound in this range does not produce coloring to the spectrum as earlier reflections would.

3. ACOUSTIC RETROREFLECTORS

This paper considers only retroreflectors, *i.e.* those returning the incident sound to the direction of the source (Fig. 2). Such reflectors have been in use also in electromagnetic waves, *e.g.* with navigation radars [1, 2]. The phenomenon of retroreflection occurs with light as well, as can be seen in Fig. 3.

The minimum size of the reflector is determined by the longest wavelength to be reflected efficiently. The frequency range that is the most important for this application is the middle audio range from about 400 Hz to about 2 kHz, where the perception of spatial characteristics are at its best. This was verified in a series of field tests, where the reflection was artificially produced with a (guitar) loudspeaker.

4. TEST ARRANGEMENT

Measurements were conducted in a semi-anechoic chamber to collect data to answer the following questions:

- What geometrical features are needed to get an adequate reflection?
- How do reflectors of different shapes and in different placements operate acoustically?
- What is the operative coverage angle of a single reflector?

The right-angled retroreflector made of water-tight veneer of size 60 cm x 60 cm was used as a reference.

Figure 2. Principle of the corner retroreflector illustrated with sound rays [2].

Figure 3. (a) An optical retroreflector, consisting of two mirrors at right angles, displaying the single-reflection mirror images of a candle on the sides and the double-reflection image behind the hinge of the mirrors. In this case the floor reflections are not specular but diffuse and thus blurred. (b) A single and double retroreflection from the reference device as seen from a camera with flashlight. The strong double reflection is around the hinge and at the left edge, the single reflection is visible partially (90° opening and oblique incidence).

This material was used in all tested devices. Only the corner reflector construction, as in Fig. 2, was tested.

The study methodology was to compare the frequency responses of the reflections from the retroreflector in different configurations. The reflection response was computed from the impulse responses obtained from a Farina-type sweep signal [5]. The magnitude axis in all figures is scaled so that the average magnitude of the direct sound corresponds to 0 dB.

The measurements were conducted in the large anechoic chamber of the Aalto University. The measurement setup consisted of a Genelec 8030A active monitor, a Brüel&Kjaer 4191 free-field microphone, and a MOTU UltraLite mk3 audio interface. The used measurement and analysis software was Matlab. Furthermore, the metal-net floor of the anechoic chamber was covered with 2 m by 7 m laminate flooring in order to create a semi-anechoic chamber for the reflectors. Figure 4 shows photos of the measurement setup.

The loudspeaker and microphone were positioned at one end of the laminate flooring with the reflector at the other end. The distance between the microphone and the reflector was approximately 4 m. As shown in Fig. 4(a), the microphone was positioned just in front of the loudspeaker in order to capture the reflected sound waves before being scattered by the loudspeaker.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4. (a) Microphone and sound source, (b) a V-shaped reference retroreflector, widely opened (over 170°), and (c) an L-shaped retroreflector with differing wing lengths.

Figure 5. Example of impulse response with emitted sound on the left and the reflected sound well after 20 ms.

Figure 5 shows an example impulse response of a measurement, where the direct and reflected sounds are clearly separated. As can be seen, the direct sound starts around 1 ms, whereas the reflected sound appears around 24.5 ms. Thus, the delay between the direct and reflected

sound is approximately 23.5 ms, which corresponds to sound traveling 8 m at the speed of 340 m/s.

5. MEASUREMENTS

We tested three basic types of retroreflectors. Figures 6 and 7 show the frequency responses from a test series with the reference device, and figures 8 and 9 a test series with lower but longer devices, with the incidence angle being varied.

Figure 6. Reflection responses of the reference device with opening angles smaller than 90°. The black lines show the cases of 90° and without reflector (WR).

Figure 6 shows that in the range of interest, from 400 Hz to 2 kHz, the reflection response decreases systematically as the 'receiving area' of the reflector becomes smaller. Above 3 kHz the response drops quickly. The opening angle of 60° makes an exception and is better than others. This may be explained by the fact that this angle creates a formation of six coinciding images, just as 90° forms four efficient coinciding mirror images. Other opening angles do not create such simple image formations.

Figure 7. Reflection responses of the reference device with opening angles larger than 90°. The black lines show the cases of 90° and without the reflector (WR).

In Fig.7, a dramatic drop in the reflection response is apparent in the frequency range of interest and beyond for opening angles exceeding 90° upto the angle 180°, which corresponds to a single board with one mirror image. In fact, an opening of 100° gives the weakest reflection of all the measured opening angles, despite its physical similarity to a 90° reflector.

Figure 8. Reflection responses of a lower but longer reflector with equal wings for different incident angles. The black lines show the cases of 90° and without the reflector (WR).

Figure 9. Reflection responses of a lower but longer reflector with unequal wings for different incident angles. The black lines show the cases of 90° and without the reflector (WR).

For incidence angle tests with lower but longer retroreflectors (responses in Figures 8 and 9), we used a scale where 45° means that one of the wings points directly towards the sound source and thus is invisible from the source.

Figure 8 indicates that the reflectivity of a symmetrical retroreflector is excellent for a wide range of incident angles (80° wide in practical use) with only the extreme of 40° showing more peaks and dips in the frequency response. Also, the L-shaped retroreflector keeps the reflection strong over a wide incidence angle range, as seen from the response in Fig. 9. Interestingly, it shows less peaks and dips and less variance between the incidence angles. This makes the L-shaped retroreflector more suitable than the symmetrical, V-shaped reflector. At 10° there is a significant dip just above 600 Hz, but so was there a similar dip in the V-shaped retroreflector as well, but at 40° incidence. Furthermore, dips in the frequency response are not perceived as clearly as peaks, if at all.

6. USER EXPERIMENTS

The same reflectors were also tested in real situations: in real music and festivity halls, the rehearsal room of a symphony orchestra, in outdoor performance venues and in an anechoic chamber.

Figure 10. A right-angled V-shaped retroreflector tested with the Jyväskylä Sinfonia in the rehearsing room among chairs and music stands.

Players of Jyväskylä Sinfonia stated that in a group performance the panels opened the possibility to hear all the performers. In a quartet formation the Viola player heard the first violin 'for the first time', not only the adjacent players, and in an orchestra configuration, all players noted an improvement in hearing the ensemble as a whole. Four reflectors of the type shown in Fig.10 and wider were tested.

Another test series was made with professional viola player Teemu Kupiainen, who has an extensive side career in playing Bach on the streets, including in Africa, China and India.

Figure 11. Violist Teemu Kupiainen with document microphones at both ears and the sound recorder for the simulated reflection signal in front. The cable leads the reflection signal to the loudspeaker.

For the tests, we created artificial reflection with loudspeaker at twice the distance of a retroreflector from the performer. The level was thus controllable and could be played back separately. The sound at the musician's ears was recorded (see Fig.11). The results in Fig.12 show that in an anechoic room a much weaker reflection is needed (-40 to -70 dB) and tolerated (-20 to -40 dB) than in a more normal and reverberant room. Even -5 dB is tolerable and as loud a reflection level as -15 dB may be needed to have a noticeable effect. The signal spectrum in both cases is the total sound coming to the ears of the performer, with adjustments for less bass and treble, which were found annoying.

Figure 12. Empirical SPL range of a favourable added reflection for a violist 5 m away from reflector (a) in an anechoic chamber and (b) in a room with 1.5 s long reverberation time. The lower edge of the red area represents the threshold level of noticing the reflection and the upper edge the level that is experienced as too loud and annoying.

Thus, the study implies that simple, portable retroreflectors can be successfully used in performance situations where the performers feel that the acoustics have inadequate ensemble balance or timbre control. The most promising construction is L-shaped two-board corner reflector, with opening angle not exceeding 90° (Fig. 13). This reflector is effective if all performers are within 80° seen from the reflector.

Figure 13. A low L-shaped retroreflector being tested by a speech coach in the Festivity hall of Helsinki University.

7. CONCLUSION

This paper has focused on the use of acoustic retroreflectors to replace monitor loudspeakers in music performances. The retroreflectors consist of two reflecting panels placed on a hard floor at a right angle. When a retroreflector is positioned at a suitable distance from the performers, it can reflect each player's own sound back to them, thus providing an unplugged approach to stage monitoring. An appropriate distance is one where the reflections arrive at the player with a delay of about 20 to 50 ms, since then the player's own sound is reinforced but a distinct echo is not perceived.

Acoustic measurements on retroreflectors were conducted in an anechoic chamber, which was converted to a semi-anechoic space by using laminate flooring. We measured the impulse response of a basic V-shaped retroreflector made of two 60 cm x 60 cm boards. The opening angle of the hinged retroreflector could be freely adjusted. The best reflection was observed the boards were at the right angle. When the opening angle was decreased, the reflection weakened mainly at frequencies

above 3 kHz. However, at lower frequencies, the retroreflector still worked fairly well with the magnitude of the reflection decreasing by less than 10 dB even in the case of a very narrow 40° opening angle. However, increasing the opening angle quickly destroys the reflection. A 100° opening angle leads to 10 to 25 dB weaker reflections, depending on the frequency, than of a right angle, making such a configuration useless in practice. It is recommended that the angle between the panels be adjusted very close to 90° or slightly smaller but not larger.

Additionally, longer and lower, 30 cm tall, retroreflectors were investigated. The dependence of the magnitude of the reflection on the incident angle of sound was varied. The data show that the retroreflector produces a strong reflection for a wide range of incident angles, with only narrow notches appearing in the magnitude response at some frequencies. This verifies the basic assumption that a retroreflector can send the sound back to (almost) any direction.

User tests with professional and amateur musicians and with a speech coach confirm our belief that a retroreflector placed in front of the performer can provide helpful auditory feedback, when other natural reflections are missing. Retroreflectors can indeed replace electro-acoustic monitoring in a music performance, when microphones are undesirable or electricity is unavailable. The most obvious uses for acoustic retroreflectors are acoustic music performances in large halls or outdoors in a square or in a park, for example.

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9. REFERENCES

- [1] E. J. Heller, *Why You Hear What You Hear*. Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2013.
- [2] Retroreflector, Corner reflector - Wikipedia
- [3] T. Lokki and J. Pätynen, Lateral reflections are favorable in concert halls due to binaural loudness. *Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, vol. 130, no. 5, pp. EL345-EL351, Nov. 2011.
- [4] J. Dammerud, Stage acoustics - a Literature review. Akutek Info, 2006. http://www.akutek.info/Papers/JJD_stage_acoustics.pdf
- [5] A. Farina, Simultaneous measurement of impulse response and distortion with a swept-sine technique, in *AES 108th Convention*, Paris, France, February 2000.